

Towards Detection of Analytes in Biotissues Using Twisted Light with Orbital Angular Momentum

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Abstract: This study explores OAM beams for analyte sensing in biological tissues. Demonstrating robust phase memory, our approach enables non-invasive glucose detection in scattering media, offering a highly sensitive optical technique for biomedical diagnostics. © 2025 The Authors

1. Introduction

Although the use of polarized light to study various properties of objects has been extensively utilized in material and life sciences [1], the interaction of shaped light, such as radially or azimuthally polarized light carrying Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM), with biological tissues remains largely unexplored and has only recently been recognized as a practical tool [2]. This new technological approach presents exciting possibilities for advanced sensing and imaging, potentially offering a new type of optical contrast. It has been recently demonstrated that OAM beams exhibit high sensitivity to refractive index variations, detecting changes on the level of 10^{-6} [3]. This property stems from the spiral phase modulation, where a small refractive index gradient induces measurable phase retardation and an observable twist in the OAM beam's wavefront. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that OAM beams can maintain their phase integrity even while propagating through highly scattering environments [3, 4]. Despite significant scattering, the initial OAM phase remains consistently preserved and is distinctly observable within the resulting speckle patterns. This robustness highlights the potential of OAM beams for sensing applications in complex optical media and turbid environments. In this paper, we further explore the application of Laguerre-Gaussian (LG) beams with OAM for sensing biologically important analytes (e.g., glucose) in/through biotissue and tissue-like scattering media.

2. Materials and methods

The measurement setup is based on the Mach-Zehnder interferometer (Fig. 1). A Gaussian beam ($\lambda = 633$ nm) is transformed into a Laguerre-Gaussian (LG) beam carrying OAM ($\ell = \pm 1, \pm 2$, etc.) using an optical phase modulator (Holoeye, Germany) operating in a reflection mode. The generated LG beam then propagates through a glass cuvette with an internal thickness of 3.6 mm, featuring an attached scattering layer (phantom or skin sample) with a specific optical depth $OD = d/l^*$ ranging from 2 to 10, where d is the thickness of the scattering layer and l^* is a corresponding transport length.

Fig. 1. Schematics of the measurement setup: LG beam, carrying OAM produced by a spatial light modulator, propagates through a cuvette containing the probed medium with an attached scattering phantom. The transmitted LG beam then interferes with a reference plane wave, derived from an initially expanded Gaussian beam. The resulting interference patterns are analyzed to extract the corresponding intensity and phase distributions.

The cuvette was filled with an aqueous solution of D(+) glucose powder (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) maintained at a controlled temperature of 21°C, with a concentration (C_{gl}) varying between 50 and 150 mg/dL, corresponding to the normal physiological range in humans [5]. The procedure of phantom preparation is detailed in [6]. Fresh porcine skin was obtained from a local grocery store and carefully placed between glass slides to minimize evaporation during measurements. The phase twist of the transmitted LG beam was analyzed using a CMOS camera (Thorlabs, USA) by examining its interference with an expanded Gaussian beam, which acted as a reference plane wave.

3. Results and conclusions

Using the developed experimental setup and an off-axis holographic phase retrieval approach [3], we obtained the azimuthal phase distributions of LG beams with $\ell = \pm 3$ after transmission through the scattering object and a cuvette filled with an aqueous glucose solution. The resulting phase maps for the case $\ell = +3$ are presented in Fig. 2.

As shown in Fig. 2a, the transparent medium preserves the characteristic helical phase structure of the LG beam, as expected. Additionally, the phase shift induced by increasing glucose concentration is clearly recorded (green spiral in Fig. 2a). In the low-scattering regime (Fig. 2b, $d/l^* = 2$), the helical phase pattern remains distinguishable but exhibits some distortion. However, the retrieved phase values within a specific beam region exhibit a similar trend of phase increase with rising glucose concentration. A comparable phase response is also observed for the strongly scattering medium ($d/l^* = 9.6$), as shown in Fig. 2c. This behavior can be attributed to the inherent phase memory of OAM beams, as previously demonstrated in [3].

Fig. 2. Phase changes/twist determined by the increase in glucose concentration measured for (a) transparent medium, (b) low scattering mode ($d/l^* = 2$), (c) diffuse scattering mode ($d/l^* = 9.6$), and (d) through *ex vivo* porcine skin. The color map at the bottom of the cylinder shows the typical azimuthal phase distribution in the corresponding case. The green spiral indicates the phase change caused by the increase in glucose concentration. The measurements have been performed with $\ell = +3$.

Fig. 2d presents the retrieved phase structure measured through an *ex vivo* porcine skin sample. The observed phase pattern closely resembles the one seen in the diffuse scattering regime (Fig. 2c), suggesting that the porcine skin exhibits similar scattering properties. This similarity confirms the validity of the prepared phantom as an optical analog for biological tissue. Furthermore, the proposed approach allows for the retrieval of phase variations associated with changes in glucose concentration, even in real biological tissue (*ex vivo* skin). This demonstrates its potential for non-invasive glucose sensing applications.

Furthermore, we conducted a comparative analysis of glucose sensing in both biological tissue and tissue-like scattering media using LG beams with opposite OAM values ($\ell = \pm 3$). The retrieved phase changes induced by increasing glucose

concentration are presented in Fig. 3 for different scattering regimes. For the same OAM state (e.g., $\ell = +3$), a comparable linear increase in phase is observed across all examined scattering media (see Fig. 3a). However, for the left-twisted beam ($\ell = -3$, Fig. 3b), the observed phase increase is approximately 1.5 times lower than that of the right-twisted beam ($\ell = +3$, Fig. 3a).

Fig. 3. The change of the LG beam azimuthal phase caused by the increase in glucose concentration measured at different scattering regimes of the phantom layers and *ex vivo* porcine skin. The measurements have been performed with $\ell = \pm 3$.

In summary, our study demonstrates the high potential of utilization of OAM beams in the sensing of biologically important analytes such as D(+) glucose in biological tissues and tissue-like scattering media. Using the phase memory effect of OAM beams, we successfully retrieved phase variations corresponding to changes in glucose concentration, even in highly scattering environments and *ex vivo* biological tissues. The results confirm the robustness of OAM-based sensing and highlight the capacity to overcome conventional optical limitations in complex media. The observed linear phase response to glucose concentration, along with the distinction between opposite OAM states, suggests that this approach could serve as a highly sensitive method for non-invasive glucose monitoring. Future work will focus on refining the technique for *in vivo* applications and expanding its scope to other biologically relevant analytes.

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5. References

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